

NAVIGATING THE INFLUENCE OF AI: A QUALITATIVE EXPLORATION OF CHATGPT USAGE AMONG TERTIARY LEVEL STUDENTS

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Navigating the Influence of AI: A Qualitative Exploration of ChatGPT Usage among Tertiary Level Students

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Abstract

ChatGPT is a comprehensive AI tool created by OpenAI, utilizing deep learning and natural language processing to provide human-like responses in advanced conversational contexts. This study examined the experiences of tertiary-level students and offered useful insights into the impact of Artificial Intelligence technologies, such as ChatGPT, on academic learning outcomes. This research employed phenomenological inquiry and purposive sampling methods. Data was collected through in-depth interviews. The data analysis identified three themes in tertiary-level students' experiences in using ChatGPT in their academics: usage for academic assistance, efficiency and accessibility, enhancing academic output, and addressing challenges. Three themes emerged from the perceived effects of ChatGPT usage on tertiary-level students' academic performance: over-reliance on ChatGPT, positive academic impacts, and balancing AI and traditional methods. Also, three themes emerged from insights of the tertiary level students on the role of AI in education: artificial intelligence (AI) as a learning aid, ethical and responsible use of AI, and AI's role in enhancing collaboration. The study suggests that tertiary-level students must be educated on the ethical considerations of using AI and develop practical applications within the limitations of academic integrity. Instructors should foster an environment where students can critically evaluate the content and learn to differentiate AI-generated material from original ideas. Higher education institutions should play a leading role in formulating and enforcing ethical guidelines for the usage of AI so that it would be clear how AI usage would be aligned with academic integrity, privacy standards, and responsible learning practices. These would be communicated to faculty and students for their ethical use of AI.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, ChatGPT, in-depth interview, tertiary level students, Philippines*

Introduction

The use of new technology in education has intensified recently, with Artificial Intelligence-based solutions gaining popularity for improving the learning experience (Aguilar, 2024). It offers interactive learning experiences, automates administrative tasks, and aids in research processes. The technology shows promise in facilitating real-time conversations and enhancing comprehension and critical thinking (Silva & Janes, 2021). However, researchers emphasize the need for effective integration strategies and teacher understanding of ChatGPT's capabilities to maximize its educational potential (Mirzaraximov, 2023). Although AI tools provide several opportunities, ethical issues must be confronted, including disseminating misinformation and reinforcing bias (Adiguzel et al., 2023). Furthermore, AI technologies such as ChatGPT can revolutionize traditional teaching and learning methodologies yet require responsible and ethical application.

In the United States, more than fifty percent of college students perceive using AI for assignments as cheating (Garrote Jurado et al., 2023). However, over fifty percent of university students in Croatia are utilizing ChatGPT for written projects. Students predominantly utilize AI for concept generation, summarization, paraphrasing, and proofreading, but others employ it to compose sections of assignments (Črček & Patekar, 2023). The advent of ChatGPT has generated substantial worries over academic integrity, inciting discussions on modifying teaching and evaluation methodologies to integrate AI tools (Info et al., 2023). Students typically regard idea production as an ethically permissible application of AI, whereas other uses are frequently seen as unethical (Črček & Patekar, 2023). These findings highlight the pressing necessity for universities to formulate explicit norms and ethical regulations for AI utilization in higher education (Garrote Jurado et al., 2023).

Research has investigated the utilization and effects of AI technologies, specifically ChatGPT, within higher education in the Philippines. The research conducted by Hernandez et al. (2023) demonstrates that students' utilization of ChatGPT is affected by supportive conditions, habitual practices, and behavioral intentions. Faculty members acknowledge the advantages and disadvantages of ChatGPT in education, underscoring the necessity of cultivating students' critical thinking abilities (Goli-Cruz, 2024). A survey of university students indicated that AI writing helper tools are frequently utilized and regarded as beneficial for performance enhancement (Diloy et al., 2023). Concerns regarding academic integrity and the potential overdependence on AI have been articulated (Garrote Jurado et al., 2023). These results underscore institutions' need to modify curricula and procedures to guarantee responsible AI utilization while preserving educational quality and integrity.

This phenomenological qualitative research seeks to investigate the experiences of tertiary-level students and offer significant insights into the impact of Artificial Intelligence technologies, such as ChatGPT, on academic learning outcomes. This research found emerging topics about the advantages and potential drawbacks of AI utilization in education.

This study is mainly anchored in the theory of the Technological Acceptance Model (TAM) proposed by Davis (1989). The approach evaluates how consumers adopt and utilize new technologies, emphasizing perceived utility and user-friendliness. This theory serves

as an acceptable theoretical framework for examining the voluntary adoption and acceptance of new technologies, such as ChatGPT, to investigate the experiences of tertiary-level students and yield significant information on the impact of artificial intelligence tools on academic learning outcomes.

Research Questions

This study aimed to explore the influence of ChatGPT usage among tertiary-level students in their academics. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. How do tertiary-level students describe their academic experiences using ChatGPT?
2. What are the perceived effects of ChatGPT usage on tertiary-level students' academic performance?
3. What are the insights of the tertiary-level students on the role of AI in education?

Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence

Anderson et al. (2018) examined the capacity of networked AI to enhance human efficacy, which has been acknowledged. However, there are apprehensions regarding the implications of interconnected artificial intelligence on human self-governance and agency. The increasing implementation of AI systems in education, like ChatGPT, has led researchers to examine the potential effects on students' intellectual autonomy and decision-making capabilities. This concern originates from John McCarthy's 1956 idea, which posited that robots could replicate some attributes of human learning.

Recent studies by Atlas (2023), Chan and Hu (2023), and Luckin (2017) have demonstrated a progressive rise in the utilization of AI within educational institutions aimed at enhancing student learning. These specialists highlight AI's capacity to provide swift individualized feedback and accommodate various learning preferences. Educational institutions strive to involve students in the broader societal advantages that AI can provide by imparting AI knowledge.

Students' Use of ChatGPT

Despite limited research on students' utilization of ChatGPT, numerous studies on the subject, conducted under diverse conditions, have recently emerged. Singh et al. (2023) performed a study with 430 computer science students at a UK institution, utilizing a 12-item questionnaire. The findings indicated that, although students were acquainted with the tool, they did not utilize it consistently in their learning activities, perhaps due to apprehensions regarding potential misuse and a deficiency in advanced knowledge of the tool at the time of the study. The authors determined that guidance is necessary to train students to utilize ChatGPT "positively."

Ngo (2023) conducted an online survey involving 200 Vietnamese students and conducted in-person interviews with 30 to investigate their perspectives on ChatGPT. The research revealed that students reported favorable experiences with ChatGPT, commending its user-friendliness and efficiency in conserving time, acquiring information, and gaining feedback. Participants acknowledged the limitations of ChatGPT, especially the questionable authenticity of its sources and content. The author concluded that standards for ChatGPT usage are essential and that academic integrity must be promoted among students to "ensure ethical applications of ChatGPT in an academic context."

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative phenomenological design. Qualitative research is a naturalistic approach that explores lived experiences and generates non-numerical data (Awasthy, 2019; Singh, 2021). It emphasizes understanding rather than explaining phenomena, focusing on processes and patterns in contextualized settings (Nassaji, 2020). Qualitative methods include interviews, observations, and focused group discussions, with the researcher as a key instrument in data collection (Awasthy, 2019).

Moreover, phenomenological design emphasizes its application in various fields, particularly education. Homewood and Vallgård (2020) demonstrate how a phenomenological approach to self-tracking devices can capture diverse subjective experiences and challenge societal understandings of the body. Stephen (2023) explores phenomenology as a design research method, highlighting its focus on human experience and providing operational frameworks.

Further, this study employed a qualitative-phenomenological approach to explore the experiences among tertiary-level students and provide valuable insights into the use of Artificial intelligence tools like ChatGPT on the academic learning outcome.

Furthermore, Creswell (2007) noted that quantitative researchers engaged in various activities to gather data. Identifying volunteers, securing material resources, and determining the study's location are essential for acquiring precise information. Data gathering methodologies encompass documentation, interviews, surveys, focus groups, observation, and audio-visual materials. The researcher's ability to immerse themselves in the research context is crucial for interpretive accounting studies (Dewi, 2021). Ethical conduct should guide all procedural decisions, emphasizing respect and trustworthiness (Frierson-Campbell & Froehlich, 2022). Data analysis often co-occurs with data collection, involving reduction, sorting, and categorization of information (Rijali, 2019).

After data collection, the material obtained from the individual in-depth interviews was collated, transcribed, translated, and analyzed. Creswell's thematic analysis was employed due to its flexible and adaptable framework, facilitating the investigation of many research questions and goals. The importance of researchers' interpretations and reflexivity in the analysis process is emphasized. Researchers can improve the rigor and credibility of their findings by engaging in a systematic and iterative procedure.

Participants

This study utilized purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a method used in research to select participants based on specific characteristics relevant to the study objectives (Klar & Leeper, 2019). While it offers advantages in obtaining targeted samples, especially for experimental research on small intersectional identity groups, it has limitations in generalizability (Andrade, 2020).

The participants of this study were the tertiary level students. Ten (10) participants were selected for the individual in-depth interview. The selection criteria for the participants are the following: currently enrolled in a tertiary institution, a third-year student taking Bachelor of Secondary Education and Bachelor of Science in Criminology, and should have experience using ChatGPT in their academic requirements.

Instrument

In this study, the researchers used a qualitative questionnaire employing open-ended questions, which were validated by experts. The requirements that must be met to create effective data collection devices were considered while preparing the instrument. Open-ended alternatives facilitated free-formatted perspectives on the discussed themes or problems. The participants' responses can then be legitimately obtained using the instruments after they have been given this authorization. The use of structured questionnaires is preferred for several reasons, including the fact that they are the least expensive data collection method and help eliminate personal bias. It puts less pressure on participants to respond immediately and gives respondents greater anonymity. It fosters an open response to the delicate topic at hand.

Results and Discussion

Experiences of Tertiary Level Students in Using ChatGPT for their Academic

There were themes emerged as a result of the responses of the participants generated from the questions namely: Usage for Academic Assistance, Efficiency and Accessibility, Enhancing Academic Output, and Addressing Challenges.

Table 1. Themes and Core Ideas on the experiences of tertiary level students in using ChatGPT for their academic

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Usage for Academic Assistance	ChatGPT is used when students struggle to answer questions or when topics are unclear. Assists in understanding phrases and interpreting questions. Provides clarification for lessons and assistance with assignments. Offers additional ideas and valuable insights when used responsibly. Used for brainstorming ideas, drafting essays, and solving problems.
Enhancing Academic Output	Useful for creating reviewers, finding objective answers, summarizing content, and structuring sentences. Improves essay writing, organization, and academic performance. Enhance organization of thoughts and approach to challenging questions. It helps in creating better-structured sentences for academic work.
Address Challenges	Students cross-check information with other sources to ensure accuracy. Rephrasing questions or consulting alternative resources when issues arise. Verification through other tools like Google is used to ensure reliability.
Efficiency and Accessibility	ChatGPT is convenient and provides direct answers quickly. Organizes information quickly for academic purposes. Accessibility through free apps increases purposes.

Usage for Academic Assistance

The academic assistance provided by ChatGPT proved to be a significant aspect of students' experiences at the tertiary level. During the interviews, the participants shared how they used the platform to accomplish academic tasks. The participants narrated the usefulness of addressing gaps in understanding, generating ideas, and assisting in the timely completion of tasks.

As IDI-P1 shared his experience,

“I used ChatGPT when there are questions I do not know how to answer, especially those that have not been discussed yet.”

Moreover, IDI-P2 also shared that,

“ChatGPT helps us understand words or phrases, especially in essays; it acts as an interpreter or translator for specific questions.”

In addition, IDI-P4 stated that,

“Sometimes I use ChatGPT to clarify lessons I do not fully understand or to help with my assignments.”

Another participant shared her experience,

“I use ChatGPT to gain additional ideas and valuable insights for my academic work, but I always use it responsibly.” (IDI-P5)

Meanwhile, a participant also shared their experiences in using ChatGPT,

“I use ChatGT to brainstorm ideas, clarify concepts, draft essays, and solve problems. It also provides study tips and enhances productivity.” (IDI-P6)

“As an English major, I use ChatGPT to create reviewers, find objective answers, summarize literary works, and structural sentences.” (IDI-P10)

Enhancing Academic Output

Enhancing academic output showcases how tertiary-level students perceive ChatGPT as a tool to improve the quality of their academic work. The participants described using the platform to develop coherent essays, arrange their ideas, and understand complex subjects, improving their academic performance.

As expressed,

“I have seen significant improvements in my essays and overall work with ChatGPT’s help.” (IDI-P6)

Another participant agreed as he shared,

“I have noticed improvements in how I organize my thoughts and approach challenging questions.” (IDI-P7)

Moreover, IDI-P10 shared that,

“It helps me develop better-structured sentences and clearer answers for academic writing.”

Address Challenges

One of the experiences of the tertiary level students in using ChatGPT is that it helps them navigate the limitations and challenges encountered while using ChatGPT. Participants discussed approaches to deal with the problem of inaccuracies, irrelevant answers, and excessive dependence on the tool. Their experiences illustrate the need for critical evaluation, cross-checking of information sources, and reasonable use to gain the advantages of ChatGPT and limit its disadvantages.

Here are some of the experiences shared by the participants in in-depth interviews,

“I trust my understanding and cross-check ChatGPT’s outputs with other sources to ensure accuracy.” (IDI-P1)

“When ChatGPT misunderstands my questions, I rephrase them or consult other resources for clarity.” (IDI-P6)

“I verify ChatGPT’s information by searching on Google or using other sources to ensure reliability.” (IDI-P10)

Efficiency and Accessibility

The tertiary level students appreciate ChatGPT for its efficiency and accessibility of use, which has been highlighted in the responses of the participants. In addition, they appreciated the fact that it offered structured and timely feedback. It was free of charge, available on various gadgets, and accessible anytime, making it useful during tight academic schedules and deadlines.

The following participants have the same experiences in using ChatGPT,

“It is very convenient and gets straight to the point.” (IDI-P4)

“ChatGPT helps me quickly and easily organize information for academic purposes.” (IDI-P9)

“ChatGPT is accessible through a free app, which makes it very easy to use.” (IDI-P10)

The Perceived Effects of ChatGPT Usage on Tertiary-Level Students' Academic Performance

The study themes emerged from the participant's responses to the perceived effects of ChatGPT on academic performance. The themes include over-reliance on ChatGPT, positive academic impacts, and balancing AI and traditional Methods. The findings emphasize the advantages and challenges of using ChatGPT in the participants' daily academic lives. They emphasize the need for responsible usage to maximize its potential while preserving critical thinking and independent learning skills.

Over-reliance on ChatGPT

The results revealed that over-reliance on ChatGPT has raised concerns among the tertiary level students. Most participants explained that using the tool regularly reduces their capacity for critical and independent thinking, which are crucial for academic growth. They pointed out situations where the ease of using ChatGPT brought about less studying, problem-solving, and creativity. Thus, quick solutions and practical assistance provided by the instrument are worth noting; at the same time, overusing it threatens to spoil the hard

work and lead to shallow knowledge of the given subject.

Table 2. *Themes and Core Ideas on the Perceived Effects of ChatGPT Usage on Tertiary-Level Students' Academic Performance*

<i>Major Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
Over-reliance on ChatGPT	Over-reliance hampers independent thinking. Reduces problem-solving abilities. Leads to the temptation of shortcuts rather than genuine effort. Promotes superficial understanding over critical thinking. It may undermine academic integrity when overused for assignments.
Positive Academic Impact	Enhances access to information and efficiency. Improves understanding of difficult topics. Boost academic performance when used appropriately. Supports brainstorming and idea formulation. Provides flexible learning tailored to individual needs.
Balancing AI and Traditional Methods	Integration of AI with traditional methods ensures comprehensive learning. Active participation in non-digital activities complements AI use. Encourages the development of time management and prioritization skills. Ensures ethical use of AI in learning. Combines manual problem-solving with AI for verification. Requires critical evaluation of ChatGPT-generated information.

As IDI-P1 stated that,

“ChatGPT should be an aid... We should not use it to the point where ChatGPT answers our tasks.”

“Over-reliance on ChatGPT can hinder progress, especially in composing our thoughts and creativity.” (IDI-P9)

IDI-P2 added that,

“There is a risk of decreased study effort because it is tempting to rely on quick answers rather than engaging deeply.”

IDI-P4 and IDI-P7 expressed that,

“It might lead to a superficiality of topics, as students may rely on quick answers instead of deeply engaging with the material.”

“It is easy to copy-paste and not think about the tasks.”

Positive Academic Impact

Positive academic impact underscored the benefits of ChatGPT in enhancing the educational experiences of tertiary-level students. The participants emphasized that the tool improves learning efficiency by giving users fast information retrieval and explanation of complicated concepts. Several of them mentioned an increase in school performance, for instance, organizing ideas in a persuasive essay, making revision notes, or brainstorming. Additionally, ChatGPT's availability and versatility encourage students' interest in the topics as it helps them grasp more complex ideas. These benefits showcase how AI technologies can be integrated into the educational process and improve performance if operated appropriately.

IDI-P5 exclaimed that,

“It helps provides quick access to information, helps clarify complex topics, and offers personalized explanations.”

IDI-P7 added that,

“It helps me understand difficult topics, saves time, and gives me new ideas.”

Other participant also admitted,

“I've notices some improvements in my grades and the quality.” (IDI-P10)

“The advantage is we can easily brainstorm and formulat ideas.” (IDI-P2)

“It's great for learning beyond the classroom and exploring subjects in more depth.” (IDI-P3)

“It provides personalized explanations that suit my learning style.” (IDI-P5)

Balancing AI and Traditional Methods

Balancing AI and Traditional Methods highlighted the need to balance AI tools like ChatGPT and traditional learning among tertiary-level students. The participants recognized the merits of AI in terms of quick responses, customized clarification, and simplifying academic tasks. However, they emphasized the necessity of using these tools with thinking skills, independent research, and other

traditional ways of learning, such as reading textbooks and solving problems without computers, which at all times are still helpful. It is important in the sense that AI may provide efficiency to students. However, the ability to think critically, analyze situations, and learn concepts at higher levels is preserved.

It was agreed by the participants in IDI respectively,

“To balance ChatGPT use with traditional learning; I make sure to engage in activities like reading textbooks, participating in discussions, and solving problems manually.” (IDI-P6)

“I still read and search without ChatGPT to make sure I am not overdependent.” (IDI-P9)

“I use ChatGPT to save time, but I make sure to double-check its information and balance my study habits.” (IDI-P7)

“After using ChatGPT for answers, I cross-check them with textbooks and other sources.” (IDI-P6)

“It might sometimes provide inaccurate information, requiring cross-verification.” (IDI-P6)

Insights of Tertiary-Level Students on the Role of AI in Education

The study explored the insights of the tertiary -level students on the role of AI in education and the responses revealed several findings. These findings include Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a learning aid, Ethical and responsible use of AI, and AI’s role in enhancing collaboration. The students expressed their insights about the importance of artificial intelligence yet insisted on balance of use. These insights collectively provide a nuanced understanding of how AI is perceived as a tool for shaping modern educational experiences.

Table 3. Themes and Core Ideas on the Insights of Tertiary-Level Students on the Role of AI in Education

Major Themes	Core Ideas
Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a Learning Aid	AI tools provide instant access to vast information resources. AI tools act as an always-available tutor, enhancing outcomes through convenience. Personalized learning experiences cater to diverse students’ needs. AI facilitates complex topic understanding by breaking them down into manageable parts. AI enhances efficiency in research and academics, such as writing and presentations.
Ethical and Responsible Use of AI	The importance of upholding academic integrity while using AI tools. AI must be used as a guide, not as a substitute for critical thinking and creativity. Educators must foster digital literacy to teach students how to use AI responsibly. Addressing potential biases in AI outputs to ensure fair and inclusive education. A balance between traditional and AI-enhanced methods promotes well-rounded education.
AI’s Role in Enhancing Collaboration	AI tools improve communication among students and between students and educators. Shared AI platforms allow for real-time feedback and idea generation in group settings. AI aids in cross-disciplinary collaborations by offering insights in multiple fields. Virtual AI platforms encourage teamwork even in remote or hybrid learning environments.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a Learning Aid

The responses provided by the participants underscore the fact that Artificial Intelligence (AI) is of utmost importance in enhancing learning experiences. They see this new technology as an effective means of helping students learn more, faster, and with less effort, by allowing them to access information, get help whenever required, and any other facets of dealing with education problems and issues. Also, it is argued that smart resources, for example, ChatGPT and others, are efficient learners as they break down complex issues for easier comprehension and support different kinds of learners.

As this participant implored,

“AI tools are great for learning because they can provide a range of information.” (IDI-P1)

“AI can be like super-smart tutor who’s always available to help.” (IDI-P4)

IDI-P6 shared,

“AI can provide personalized learning experiences, instant feedback, and accessible resources.”

Other participants added that,

“AI like ChatGPT makes learning accessible and efficient, helping to grasp complex topics.” (IDI-P8)

“AI can improve academic writings and presentation, saving time for other learning activities.” (IDI-P10)

Ethical and Responsible Use of AI

Using artificial intelligence in education emphasizes the responsibility for ethical considerations and regulations. The tertiary-level students highlight the importance of balancing AI’s capabilities. Participants were aware of many of the negative impacts of AI, including overreliance, issues of originality, and alternative misuse. In addition, there was a concern for the fairness, privacy, and

accountability of using AI in educational contexts.

It is evident when participants shared that,

“AI raises ethical concerns like plagiarism and lack of proper citations.” (IDI-P6)

“Students must balance AI use with their own originality and critical thinking.” (IDI-P3)

“Teachers should guide students on using AI tools responsibly and ethically.” (IDI-P10)

“AI tools sometimes show bias, so we need to analyze their outputs critically.” (IDI-P5)

“AI must integrate in a way that does not overshadow traditional learning approaches.” (IDI-P6)

AI's Role in Enhancing Collaboration

Artificial intelligence perceived by tertiary level students promotes collaboration in education. According to participants, AI should act as a tool that enhances group work, communication among group members, and organizing collaborative study projects. The majority of AI tools allow for synchronous communication, immediate feedback, and individualized support, thus making teamwork more effective and inclusive. However, there should still be an opportunity for human interaction in collaboration, so AI should supplement rather than replace what is human about collaborative engagement.

As IDI-P7 expressed that,

“AI facilitates collaboration in group projects by helping with planning and communication.”

IDI-P4 added that,

“AI tools help students collaborate better by providing instant feedback on shared documents.”

IDI-P2 exclaimed that,

“AI provides resources across various fields, supporting collaboration between disciplines.”

Another participant added that,

“AI makes online group projects easier and more organized, especially in hybrid learning setups.” (IDI-P3)

Experiences of Tertiary-Level Students in Using ChatGPT for Their Academics

Four primary themes emerged from the analysis of the data collected on the participants' experiences: usage for academic assistance, enhancing academic output, addressing challenges, and efficiency and accessibility. These themes summarize the different ways students interact with ChatGPT and its pros and cons in supporting their academics.

Usage for Academic Assistance

The majority of the participants affirmed that ChatGPT has considerably helped them when it comes to performing academic tasks. They noted that the application assists them in tackling issues and topics that are challenging for them or that have not been taught in class yet. Many of them rely on ChatGPT to generate ideas, assist with the structure of their work, and find complex definitions. Participants also pointed out its importance in organizing ideas, writing essays, and providing and processing relevant data for different subjects. The ease of use and rapid delivery of precise and exhaustive information have made it a perfect tool for all individuals involved in academic work. In general, the students emphasized that using ChatGPT improves the overall learning process and their productivity as long as it is used in moderation.

The result is aligned with the study conducted by Alqadi et al. (2023), who stated that the potential of ChatGPT in generating ideas, summarizing, rephrasing, and even editing has been noted for academic purposes. In the case of L2 students, it can be beneficial in proofreading, brainstorming, and translating activities to improve their English for academic purposes (Wang, 2024). The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) has been used to gauge students' perspectives towards ChatGPT, and it was found that perceived usefulness significantly influences attitude to use the technology (Liling & Aklani, 2023). ChatGPT's scope of application also includes data collection, teamwork, and even research across multiple disciplines to enhance integration. However, the issue of academic dishonesty remains (Chukwuere, 2024).

Enhancing Academic Output

The tertiary level students perceived their experiences as ChatGPT helping enhance their academic performance. Most participants disclosed that the tool assists them in drafting coherent essays and developing and arranging their ideas in order. They mentioned its relevance in understanding complex subjects, making tackling challenging academic tasks more manageable. At the same time, many students reported that their writing ability and overall performance improved due to the use of ChatGPT. In addition, it emphasizes that if the tool is used appropriately, ChatGPT can be an effective tool for one's quest for academic achievement.

The result is congruent with the proposition of Rezaei et al. (2024), which stated that despite its advantages in brainstorming, improving language fluency, and enhancing academic writing productivity, ChatGPT poses risks of dependency and potential plagiarism. ChatGPT enhances learning designs in the educational system, reduces time spent on repetitive work, and supports researchers (Silva & Janes, 2021). It can be used for different learning purposes, such as evaluation, virtual assistance, and content creation. However, issues such as data privacy, biases, and ethical handling need to be addressed (Nikolopoulou, 2024).

Address Challenges

Another central theme from this study is how tertiary-level students address challenges when using ChatGPT. The participants mentioned that the tool does help. However, it has drawbacks, as it can sometimes offer vague, irrelevant, or even incorrect answers. Some students also stated that they feared becoming too dependent on ChatGPT and that it could hinder their creativity and ability to think critically. In order to overcome such challenges, they emphasized the need to verify information from other sources and rephrase questions to receive more precise answers. Many participants mentioned how they attempted to balance using ChatGPT as a support tool and focusing on enhancing their academic skills.

The results parallel Mosaiyebzadeh et al. (2023), which state that ChatGPT is an advanced AI-based language model that can be used in many fields, especially education and research. It has its advantages, such as helping with personalized learning and reducing the amount of work. On the other hand, it has its disadvantages, like cheating and other ethical concerns (Khan, 2023). To mitigate the issues, it has been recommended that a dimensional approach that involves experts scrutinizing, making the public participate, and creating regulatory structures be put forward. (Khan, 2023). Generating human-level conversations makes ChatGPT a beneficial resource. However, limitations and biases surrounding its use must be addressed (Deng & Lin, 2023). As ChatGPT continues to evolve, researchers emphasize the need to balance AI-assisted innovation with human expertise and address ethical concerns to ensure responsible use (Khan, 2023).

Efficiency and Accessibility

Efficiency and accessibility emphasize that ChatGPT aids in the academic tasks of students at the tertiary level. Participants rated it high on the efficiency scale as they could obtain information almost instantly, which is practical for assignments with tight deadlines. Additionally, they acknowledged its user-friendliness, stating that it is free of charge and can be augmented by an app for ease of use. The students could also state that ChatGPT enhanced their ability to complete tasks since it structured information and expressed concepts in a way that was easy to understand. This efficiency enables them to beat the deadlines and attend to other academic priorities.

The result is in line with Farrokhnia et al. (2023), who stated that education has benefited from the advent of ChatGPT, which has offered a new improvement dimension through efficiency and accessibility. Education can improve the learning environment, assist individual learners, and ease the burden of teaching. ChatGPT responses can aid education management by simplifying education management processes due to internet connectivity options (Harini, 2023). Challenges include biases, inability to comprehend adequately, and privacy issues (Samala et al., 2024). Furthermore, the raised issues regard the influence of this technology on academic honesty and even critical thinking skills (Farrokhnia et al., 2023).

The Perceived Effects of ChatGPT Usage on Tertiary-Level Students' Academic Performance

Three major themes emerged on the perceived effects of ChatGPT usage among the tertiary-level students' academic performance. The themes include over-reliance on ChatGPT, positive academic impact, and balancing AI and traditional methods. Each theme emphasizes different aspects of Chat GPT's effect on students learning, including its drawbacks and benefits in enhancing efficiency and understanding.

Over-reliance on ChatGPT

Most participants emphasized the risks associated with over-reliance on ChatGPT for academic assignments. They feared that too much tool use would harm critical thinking, creativity, and independent problem-solving abilities. Several responses suggested the need for moderation to prevent ChatGPT from being used excessively in place of actual work and thinking. It indicates that there is a need for AI to enhance learning and cognitive development instead of providing a replacement for learning.

The results align with the study of Wahyu Purwasih and Ahmad Sahnan (2023), which stated that excessive use of ChatGPT can reduce creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving ability. ChatGPT is advanced and has excellent potential as an expert tool in various fields. However, it has drawbacks, such as providing wrong answers and ethical issues, which make it necessary to be careful with its outputs and verify them (Azaria et al., 2023). User trust is one factor determining the acceptance and usage of ChatGPT, wherein higher levels of trust translate to greater intention and actual usage (Choudhury & Shamszare, 2023).

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Balancing AI and Traditional Methods

The participants underscored the need to use ChatGPT with other ways of learning appropriately. Even though they appreciated the accessibility and time-saving offered by AI, they noted the importance of doing activities that promote critical thinking, self-studying, and dealing with real-world problems. Many participants discussed integrating AI with other methods, like reading textbooks and other sources. It emphasizes the potential of technology for educational purposes but also with a great responsibility that will not hamper the fundamental skills of a student.

The result aligns with the study of Patel et al. (2023), which stated that ChatGPT offers personalized tutoring, immediate feedback, and support in various subjects, including mathematics (Patel et al., 2023). It can assist with content creation, language acquisition, and research (Nikolopoulou, 2024). However, concerns about academic integrity, data privacy, and potential misuse persist (Sain & Lama, 2024; Patel et al., 2023). Educators must balance AI-driven support and traditional teaching methods to create comprehensive learning experiences (Ramprakash et al., 2024). Implementing ChatGPT in higher education requires addressing ethical considerations and potential misuses while fostering critical thinking skills. Although ChatGPT shows promise in transforming education, it should be viewed as a complementary tool that requires human evaluation and review (Nikolopoulou, 2024).

Insights of Tertiary-Level Students on the Role of AI in Education

Based on the analysis of the data gathered from the insights from the participants, three main themes about how they view the role of AI in education, namely AI as a learning aid, ethically responsible use of AI, and AI's Role in enhancing collaboration. These themes highlight the wide range of opinions that tertiary-level students share regarding the advantages and concerns they perceive about bringing AI into education.

AI as a Learning Aid

Most of the participants emphasized the importance of AI as a learning aid. The participants show that although AI applications such as ChatGPT give fast responses, they also allow them to have easy access to information. They highlight the possibilities presented by AI for personalized support, including instant feedback. The participants share that AI-simplified concepts help them grasp complex subjects and improve their writing skills.

The findings correspond with the research conducted by Hartley et al. (2024), which asserts that ChatGPT can deliver tailored feedback, facilitate self-directed learning, and aid in content production. It has demonstrated potential in language acquisition activities, providing instantaneous feedback and tailored experiences (Xiao & Zhi, 2023). However, researchers caution that ChatGPT's responses can be superficial or contradictory, emphasizing users' need for critical evaluation (Stojanov, 2023). The tool's effectiveness in supporting self-regulated learning processes, particularly in programming education, has been demonstrated. However, its assessment capabilities have limitations (Hartley et al., 2024).

Ethical and Responsible Use of AI

Most participants shared the significance of the ethical responsibility of AI usage in education. They are all aware of how AI can transform and generate. However, there is a need to balance the usage to prevent over-reliance and loss of critical thinking and creativity. Some participants were concerned with data privacy and whether the information derived from AI tools was accurate, and some others even saw the possibility of misusing such tools in unethical activities such as plagiarism or dishonesty in academic work. Most of them asked for excellent guidelines on responsibly integrating AI into learning without replacing traditional learning methods, whereby usage would complement all learning methods. As per the participants, ethical issues should ensure the course and use of AI to empower rather than being dependent on it to foster academic integrity and meaningful learning outcomes.

This result aligns with Mhlanga's (2023) assertion regarding the ethical considerations and appropriate utilization of ChatGPT in educational contexts, emphasizing the necessity for privacy, fairness, and transparency in its implementation. A new theoretical framework grounded in responsible AI principles has been introduced to examine the ethical implications of ChatGPT and to alleviate unforeseen outcomes (Lababidi, 2024). The ethical application of ChatGPT in leadership and strategic decision-making entails intricate concerns regarding openness, fairness, privacy, long-term consequences, and risk management (Basir et al., 2023). A conceptual framework has been developed for teaching and learning environments to support cognitive flexibility and critical thinking using AI chatbots responsibly (Chauncey & McKenna, 2023).

AI's Role in Enhancing Collaboration

According to the participants, one of the most vital contributions of AI is towards collaboration among students and educators, who are working to bring learner collaboration. The AI tools are likely effective facilitators through their efficiency in employing better

communication, organizing group projects, and sharing resources. Among the recognition captured on AI was its ability to give instant feedback, reduce costly collaborative activities, adapt to diverse learning styles, and all that within group settings. On the other hand, such AI platforms break barriers to allow students to collaborate remotely while accessing shared resources. Despite its benefits, participants also noted that collaboration's human element should not be overshadowed, as interpersonal interactions remain essential for building teamwork and social skills.

The result parallels Oguine et al. (2023), which stated that ChatGPT has shown high effectiveness in improving collaboration. In the arts, it aids in generating ideas, overcoming creative blocks, and facilitating remote collaboration. However, ethical concerns regarding authorship and authenticity persist (Zhu et al., 2024). ChatGPT integration significantly increases trust in human-robot collaboration by enabling more effective communication and natural interaction between humans and robots. The technology's ability to understand and respond appropriately to human language nuances contributes to building trust in collaborative settings (Ye et al., 2023).

Conclusions

Artificial Intelligence (AI) in higher education offers considerable opportunities and impediments. This study examined the experiences of tertiary-level students. It offered valuable insights into the impact of Artificial Intelligence technologies, such as ChatGPT, on academic learning outcomes. The researchers conducted in-depth interviews with chosen tertiary-level students.

Moreover, the participants expressed that the application assists them in tackling issues and topics that are challenging for them or that have not been taught in class yet. Many tertiary-level students rely on ChatGPT to generate ideas, assist with the structure of their work, and find complex definitions. Participants also pointed out its importance in organizing ideas, writing essays, and providing and processing relevant data for different subjects. The ease of use and rapid delivery of precise information has made it a perfect tool for all individuals involved in academic work. In general, the students emphasized that using ChatGPT improves the overall learning process and their productivity as long as it is used in moderation.

To conclude, the ethical consideration in using AI in education is significant. Although AI can transform academic work, it is important to balance its uses to prevent over-reliance and foster critical thinking and creativity at best. This would include keys such as the principles of data privacy, the truthfulness of AI content, or exposing a new ground that might be seen as unethical, such as using AI for purposes like plagiarism or dishonesty in academic work. Clear and practical guidelines on the use of AI prerequisite education. These ethical considerations underpin empowering learners, maintaining academic integrity, and affording more meaningful learning outcomes.

References

- Alqadi, R., Alrbaiyan, A., Alrumayyan, N., Alqahtani, N., & Najjar, A.B. (2023). Exploring the User Experience and the Role of ChatGPT in the Academic Writing Process. *2023 Congress in Computer Science, Computer Engineering, & Applied Computing (CSCE)*, 1082-1089.
- Andrade, C. (2020). The Inconvenient Truth About Convenience and Purposive Samples. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 43, 86 - 88.
- Awasthy, R. (2019). Nature of Qualitative Research. *Methodological Issues in Management Research: Advances, Challenges, and the Way Ahead*.
- Aguiar, J.J. (2024). ChatGPT as an educational support tool: an analysis of its potential in the teaching and learning process. *Caderno Pedagógico*.
- Azaria, A., Azoulay-Schwartz, R., & Reches, S. (2023). ChatGPT is a Remarkable Tool—For Experts. *Data Intelligence*, 6, 240-296.
- Basir, A., Puspitasari, E., Aristarini, C.C., Sulastri, P.D., & Almaududi Ausat, A.M. (2023). Ethical Use of ChatGPT in the Context of Leadership and Strategic Decisions. *Jurnal Minfo Polgan*.
- Chauncey, S.A., & McKenna, H.P. (2023). A framework and exemplars for ethical and responsible use of AI Chatbot technology to support teaching and learning. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*.
- Choudhury, A., & PhD, M.B. (2023). Investigating the Impact of User Trust on Adoption and Use of ChatGPT: A Survey Analysis.
- Chukwuere, J.E. (2024). Today's Academic Research: The Role of ChatGPT Writing. *Journal of Information Systems and Informatics*.
- Črček, N., & Patekar, J. (2023). Writing with AI: University Students' Use of ChatGPT. *Journal of Language and Education*.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *Management Information Systems Quarterly*, 13(3), 319-340.
- Dewi, I.G. (2021). Understanding Data Collection Methods in Qualitative Research: The Perspective Of Interpretive Accounting Research. *Journal of Tourism Economics and Policy*.

- Diloy, M.A., Comparativo, C.P., Reyes, J.C., Eusebio, B.J., & Morona, L.I. (2023). Exploring the Landscape of AI Tools in Student Learning: An analysis of commonly utilized AI Tools at a university in the Philippines. *Proceedings of the 2023 6th Artificial Intelligence and Cloud Computing Conference*.
- Farrokhnia, M., Banihashem, S.K., Noroozi, O., & Wals, A.E. (2023). A SWOT analysis of ChatGPT: Implications for educational practice and research. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 61, 460 - 474.
- Frierson-Campbell, C., & Froehlich, H.C. (2022). Selected Procedures for Gathering, Analyzing, and Reflecting on Qualitative Data. *Inquiry in Music Education*.
- Garrote Jurado, R., Pettersson, T., & Zwierewicz, M. (2023). STUDENTS' ATTITUDES TO THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE. *ICERI2023 Proceedings*.
- Goli-Cruz, M.J. (2024). Perceptions of Higher Education Faculty Regarding the Use of Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (ChatGPT) in Education. *International Journal on Open and Distance e-Learning*.
- Harini, H. (2023). The Role of ChatGPT in Improving the Efficiency of Education Management Processes. *Indo-MathEdu Intellectuals Journal*.
- Hartley, K., Hayak, M., & Ko, U.H. (2024). Artificial Intelligence Supporting Independent Student Learning: An Evaluative Case Study of ChatGPT and Learning to Code. *Education Sciences*.
- Hernandez, A.A., Abisado, M.B., Rodriguez, R.L., & Imperial, J.M. (2023). Predicting the Use Behavior of Higher Education Students on ChatGPT: Evidence from the Philippines. *2023 IEEE International Conference on Teaching, Assessment and Learning for Engineering (TALE)*, 1-7.
- Homewood, S., & Vallgård, A. (2020). Putting Phenomenological Theories to Work in the Design of Self-Tracking Technologies. *Proceedings of the 2020 ACM Designing Interactive Systems Conference*.
- Info, A., Sullivan, M., Kelly, A., & Mclaughlan, P. (2023). ChatGPT in higher education: Considerations for academic integrity and student learning. 1.
- Khan, M.S. (2023). A Multidimensional Approach Towards Addressing Existing and Emerging Challenges in the Use of ChatGPT. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
- Klar, S., & Leeper, T.J. (2019). Identities and Intersectionality: A Case for Purposive Sampling in Survey-Experimental Research. *Experimental Methods in Survey Research*.
- Lababidi, S. (2024). A Critical Evaluation of ChatGPT's Adherence to Responsible Artificial Intelligence Principles. *Information Sciences with Applications*.
- Livberber, T., & Ayvaz, S. (2023). The impact of Artificial Intelligence in academia: Views of Turkish academics on ChatGPT. *Heliyon*, 9.
- Mahapatra, S. (2024). Impact of ChatGPT on ESL students' academic writing skills: a mixed methods intervention study. *Smart Learn. Environ.*, 11, 9.
- Mhlanga, D. (2023). Open AI in Education, the Responsible and Ethical Use of ChatGPT Towards Lifelong Learning. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
- Mosaiyebzadeh, F., Pouriye, S., Parizi, R.M., Dehbozorgi, N., Dorodchi, M., & Macêdo Batista, D. (2023). Exploring the Role of ChatGPT in Education: Applications and Challenges. *Proceedings of the 24th Annual Conference on Information Technology Education*.
- Nikolopoulou, K. (2024). Generative Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education: Exploring Ways of Harnessing Pedagogical Practices with the Assistance of ChatGPT. *International Journal of Changes in Education*.
- Oguine, M.B., Oguine, C.G., & Oguine, K.J. (2023). My Machine and I: ChatGPT and the Future of Human-Machine Collaboration in Africa. *ArXiv*, abs/2310.13704.
- Randa Liling, J., & Anas Aklani, S. (2023). Analysis of ChatGPT Usage to Support Student Lecture Assignments. *JURNAL FASILKOM*.
- Rijali, A. (2019). ANALISIS DATA KUALITATIF. *Alhadharah: Jurnal Ilmu Dakwah*.
- Rueda, M.M., Fernández-Cerero, J., Fernández-Batanero, J.M., & López-Meneses, E. (2023). Impact of the Implementation of ChatGPT in Education: A Systematic Review. *Comput.*, 12, 153.
- Silva, A.D., & Janes, D.D. (2021). The Emergence of ChatGPT and its Implications for Education and Academic Research in the 21st

Century. Review of Artificial Intelligence in Education.

Stojanov, A. (2023). Learning with ChatGPT 3.5 as a more knowledgeable other: an autoethnographic study. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20, 1-17.

Mirzaraximov, M. (2023). THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE-BASED CHATBOTS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM. *Scientific journal of the Fergana State University*.

Nassaji, H. (2020). Good qualitative research. *Language Teaching Research*, 24, 427 - 431.

Patel, R., Bajaj, P., Kumar, A., Kumari, A., Rai, V., & Kumar, S. (2023). ChatGPT in the Classroom: A Comprehensive Review of the Impact of ChatGPT on Modern Education. 2023 11th International Conference on Intelligent Systems and Embedded Design (ISED), 1-6.

Pawar, P.P., Salve, K.B., & Patil, R.R. (2023). "Impact of ChatGPT on Student's Education: A Comprehensive analysis of positive and negative effects". *Journal of Advanced Zoology*.

Samala, A.D., Zhai, X., Aoki, K., Bojić, L., & Žikić, S. (2024). An In-Depth Review of ChatGPT's Pros and Cons for Learning and Teaching in Education. *Int. J. Interact. Mob. Technol.*, 18, 96-117.

Stephen, A. (2023). Methodological thoughts: Phenomenology. *Blucher Design Proceedings*.

Wahyu Purwasih & Ahmad Sahnan (2023). Deviant acts in the use of ChatGPT: An analytical study of student behavior. *INSANIA: Jurnal Pemikiran Alternatif Kependidikan*.

Wang, Y. (2024). Reviewing the Usage of ChatGPT on L2 students' English Academic Writing Learning. *Journal of Education, Humanities and Social Sciences*.

Xiao, Y., & Zhi, Y. (2023). An Exploratory Study of EFL Learners' Use of ChatGPT for Language Learning Tasks: Experience and Perceptions. *Languages*.

Ye, Y., You, H., & Du, J. (2023). Improved Trust in Human-Robot Collaboration With ChatGPT. *IEEE Access*, 11, 55748-55754.

Zhu, S., Wang, Z., Yuan, Z., Jiang, Y., Guo, M., Zhang, X., & Gao, Z. (2024). Exploring the impact of ChatGPT on art creation and collaboration: Benefits, challenges and ethical implications. *Telematics and Informatics Reports*.

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